

Effect of Concentrated Language Encounter Instructional Strategy on Reading Skills Among Primary School Pupils in Dutsin-ma, Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper investigates Effect of Concentrated Language Encounter Instructional Strategy on Reading Skills Among Primary School Pupils in Dutsin-ma, Katsina State, Nigeria Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study utilized quasi experimental design. The population of the study consists of all pupils in Demonstration School, Isa Kaita College of Education during the 2023/2024 academic session in Dutsin-ma Katsina state. 16 primary four pupils were selected using multi-stage sampling technique to constitute the Sample size of the study The instruments used for data collection are included: Sight Word Recognition Test of 100 High Frequency English Words (SWRTHFEW), Sentence Comprehension Tests (SCT) and Reading of New Texts Tests (RNTT). The coefficient of stability obtained for each instrument is 0.98 for SWRTHFEW, 1.00 for SCT and 0.99 for RNTT. The treatment consisted of Concentrated Language Encounter module one. Data were administered, research questions were answered using bar chart and hypothesis tested using t-test unrelated sample at 0.05 level of significance. The Results indicated that. Post-tests mean scores of pupils in the experimental group which received intervention in using literacy were significantly higher than that of those in control group who used conventional method. It was concluded that the results and responses of the samples the differences and the performance of school children after intervention proves the effectiveness of this method, the improvement in children performance in general was mainly due to the intervention given to them.the study recommends the use of Concentrated Language Encounter method in acquisition of literacy skills with non-readers.

Keyword; Language Encounter, Instructional Strategy, Reading Skills.

Introduction

One of the objectives of Primary Education stated in the National Policy on Education (2012) was to inculcate permanent literacy and the ability to communicate effectively. But there would appear to be a confusion on how to achieve these objectives. For example, Unoh (2014) observed that the task of teaching children how to read in schools in Nigeria has been left entirely to the individual teachers. These teachers probably do not understand the great intellectual significance of the simple task KIU Journal of Social Sciences 170 reading. For this reason, most of our Primary and Secondary School learners cannot read simple texts that are meant for them to read independently. There are several causes for reading failure among our pupils in Demonstration School Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma Katsin State. However, the children in the lower primary school are taught how to read in English (L2) before they actually acquired the oral proficiency in the language. Finocchiaro, (2015) stated in her stages of teaching and learning of reading in second language (L2) that “students read material they have learned to say very well”. This statement is supporting the view that children can read well in the language they have acquired oral proficiency. In line with this, Unoh (2012) further stated that his ultimate aim of what learning to read and reading to learn, is that the skills associated with listening and speaking are developed before that of reading and writing. One other probable problem which is highly suspected that makes reading very difficult among children in the state is that children are taught how to read English language books by oral recitation. This is when teachers read sentences inside their textbooks and children repeat after the teacher. In most cases, these children memorize the sentences and only pronounce word without identifying the prints that represent these words and teacher assume that these children can read. One other possible cause of reading failure among these pupils is the issue of automatic promotion of pupils, especially in junior primary classes regardless of the child’s performance in the former class. This negligence of individual differences by teachers to the researcher might again be a contributing factor in the production of graduates at these levels without being able to read simple books independently. Other possible cause of reading failure among our pupils in the State are lack of text and story books and lack

of teachers using appropriate methods to teach children how to read. These problems and many others have left our pupils under a number of disadvantages. For example, the majority of the children leave primary schools without being fully literate. It is with this view in mind that the researcher wants to investigate the extent to which Concentrated Language Encounter can help develop reading skills among pupils in primary schools.

Considering the high rate of reading failure in both public and private schools in the State reading specialists are faced with the challenge of providing effective remediation. Children with problems in reading English as second language have not been taught how to speak English before they are taught how to read it. Which means that children have not been taught in a way they will learn how to read effectively. Similarly, teachers have not been using appropriate strategies that would promote effective reading in English. For effective reading, teachers must use the skills to help children who come to school to learn how to read in English. Specifically, it is important to consider how reading specialists can draw on the language skills the children already have as they come to school in teaching them to read effectively in English. This study will help the researcher to find out if the Concentrated Language Encounter Method when properly used during intervention will help to improve the children's ability to recognize sight vocabulary and comprehend printed materials in English.

Objective of the Study

The research is designed mainly to investigate the effect of Concentrated Language Encounter Method in development of beginning reading skills among primary school pupils who are non-readers. Specifically:

1. To investigate mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method?

Research Hypotheses

1. H_{01} There is no significant difference in mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method.

Methodology

This study utilized the quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test, post-test control group design. The design featured two groups. Subjects were randomly selected and assigned to experimental and control groups (R). Both the experimental and control groups were administered the post-test (O). Only the experimental group was exposed to the treatment (X) on literacy using Concentrated Language Encounter Method while the control group received no treatment but was taught through conventional method. A sample of 16 non – readers who have already received at least three and a half years of primary education were selected after the administration of pre-test which is the 100 English high frequency words for Nigerian children (Umolu, 2014). Eight (8) nonreaders formed the experimental group and another eight (8) for the control group. The instruments used for the study includes: Sight Word Recognition Test of 100 High Frequency English Words (SWRTHFEW), Sentence Comprehension Tests (SCT) and Reading of New Texts Tests (RNTT). The coefficient of stability obtained for each instrument is 0.98 for SWRTHFEW, 1.00 for SCT and 0.99 for RNTT. These were established through test re-test method.

Presentation of Results

Research Question one

What is the mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method?

Table 1 English Sight Word Vocabulary before Intervention. Experimental Group

Child Score out 100 Word	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Average
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A1X	1	2	1	1	1	1
A2X	2	2	2	2	2	2
A3X	1	1	1	1	1	1
A4X	1	2	1	1	1	1
A5X	2	1	2	2	3	1
A6X	2	2	2	2	2	2
A7X	1	2	1	1	1	2
A8X	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 2 English Sight Word Vocabulary before Intervention. Control Group

Child Score out 100 Word						
	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Average
B1	1	2	1	1	1	1
B2	2	1	2	2	3	2
B3	2	1	2	2	2	2
B4	1	2	1	1	1	1
B5	1	2	2	1	1	1
B6	2	1	2	2	2	2
B7	2	1	2	2	2	2
B8	1	2	1	1	1	1

The pre-test of the ability of primary school children who are non- readers in both experimental and control groups to read the 100 English Sight Words shows that they are at the same level and are all nonreaders.

The test scores are shown in Table 1 & 2.

Hypothesis one

H_{01} There is no significant difference in mean performance/skill acquisition scores of pupils taught vocabulary using Concentrated Language Encounter and those exposed to lecture method.

Table 5 Group Difference in English Sight Vocabulary t-test

	N	X	St	df	t-cal	P-value
Experimental Group	8	9	1.88			
Control	8	3.16	0.79	14	253.23	0.000

Control Group 83.16 0.79 $P < .05$ For degree of freedom of 6 and level of significance at .05, with P. value of 0.000, the calculated t-test statistics is given at 253.23 which is significant beyond 0.05 level. Hypothesis one was therefore rejected in favour of primary school children who are non- readers in the experimental group. The general findings from the result showed that primary school children who are non- readers who received intervention in literacy skill have higher mean scores in acquisition of English sight vocabulary than the primary school children who are non- readers who did not received intervention.

Discussion of Findings

In analyzing the reading level of children in both the control and experimental groups before exposure to CLE, the research findings, presented in Table 1, showed that none of them could identify more than three of the 100 high frequency words. Thus, they were all non-readers because, according to the guidelines for identification of reading problems, anyone who read less than 10 of the first 25 words during assessment is considered to be a non-reader. The reading levels of learners should be given priority attention in order to prepare them for the acquisition of a sight vocabulary which is very crucial in learning to read. Words are the building blocks of comprehension and word recognition is the foundation of reading process. It is recognized that without the ability to recognize words in continuous text quickly and accurately, this goal cannot be achieved. According to Rupley, Logan, and Nichols (2012, sight vocabulary is a key component of effective reading instruction. Similarly, Flood and Robb (2014) buttressed the fact that both fluency and comprehension are affected by sight vocabulary knowledge. The findings revealed that there is a significant difference in the acquisition of English sight vocabulary of primary

school children in experimental group with those in the control group. However, the significant difference which was observed in this study showed that Concentrated Language Encounter was very effective in facilitating learners' acquisition of sight words in English. This is consistent with the findings of Rayner and Pallatsek (2013) that reading involves visual discrimination and independent identification of words. That is, if a child can differentiate between letters and words perceived, then the visual discrimination is possible. When a child is able to identify words in isolation and read them accurately and can read sentences in a book successfully, then we can say that the child is now ready to process reading materials. Similarly, Hanson and Reynolds (2014) observed that when a child had acquired oral language proficiency, then the child moves to discriminate and attempt to read in order to identify visual, auditory and context clues. They will also substitute the consonants, the vowels of alphabets as well as attainment. They went on to say that the use of the visual auditory perception was that the child sees the word first, and then tries to sound out the word. From there, the child analyze the word to discover the graphemes (letter clues) to phonemes (sound clues), and relates this to the particular word context. The child then blends the sounds together to pronounce the word and relates its meaning in the language of the child. This they said is why Concentrated Language Encounter is effective because it deals extensively with word recognition, blended with the correct pronunciation and meaning of what was read. It was also noted that the number of words known by the child at any given age was a unique feature of that child. The findings of this study also revealed that there is a significant difference in sentence comprehension of primary four children in the experimental group as compared with that of those in the control group. The general performance of children in sentence comprehension has actually shown how effective Concentrated Language Encounter method is in aiding children in sentence comprehension. This confirmed the study carried out by Walker (2015) who stated that at the beginning of reading, it is essential that all the words to be read should be within the child's vocabulary so that he/she will be able to recognize the words which may lead him to comprehend. The author went on to explain that if a word was an ambiguous one, the teacher needs a process of selection which he operated on, so that the child can get the correct meaning of the word. This is possible when the teacher uses the word in different sentences which could give the word different meanings from each other. To further explain the importance of comprehension, Pearson and Duke (2002) stressed that comprehension guides students in becoming aware of how well they have read as they attempt to put into writing or recall what they have read.

Conclusion

The study was conducted to find out the effect of using the Concentrated Language Encounter method in developing literacy skill in primary schools in Demonstration School, Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma, Katsina State. This was based on the gap that existed in literacy training of primary school children. The variables of sight vocabulary and comprehension skills were put to test. Based on the investigation and data analysis, it is evident that primary school children could do well in literacy if appropriate method is employed. From the results and the responses of the samples, the differences in the performance of school children after intervention proved the effectiveness of this method. Therefore, it can be concluded that, the improvement in children's performance in general was mainly due to the intervention given to them.

Recommendation

It has been noticed from the results of the study conducted that, reading specialists in primary schools are needed to identify, assess and remedy reading problems in children identified as non-readers. The researcher also observed during the study that, the environment under which children learn and most often the techniques used in teaching affect the children. In most cases children who are having problems in reading are being lumped together in a class with those who have no problems with reading. This worsened their condition because no individual differences are taken into consideration by the teachers; therefore the researcher recommends that:

1. There is need for variation in teaching methods by teachers and resource personnel to cater for the less privileged ones in the class. Teaching in small groups and if possible individually should be used and the level of books used should vary according to the levels of the children.
2. Scaffolding technique as in Concentrated Language Encounter method can be used to effect change in learning to read with slow readers.
3. Training of teachers and resource teachers can be achieved by regular attendance of seminars, conferences, and workshops, especially on the techniques of how to use Concentrated Language Encounter method to minimize some of the reading problems we have in our primary schools today.

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